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Farmers' perceptions and willingness to adopt hydroponic systems: A study in Welimada, Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Hydroponics has many advantages over conventional farming, including improved nutrition management, increased quantity and productivity, shorter growth intervals for many plants, high propagation success rates, lower fertilizer costs, no pesticides or herbicides, and better use of space. This study investigates farmers' perceptions of accepting Hydroponic Systems as well as their willingness to adopt them. A survey was undertaken in Badulla District using a convenience sample of 132 vegetable farmers to discern this study's scope. The selected farmers represent a homogeneity in terms of the vegetable mix cultivated, climate, and geography, whereas heterogeneity in willingness and demographic factors. The survey findings suggest strong evidence of farmers' willingness to adopt agricultural innovations and favourable perceptions toward such technologies. The results of the probit estimation of farmers' willingness to adopt hydroponic systems indicate that the age and gender of the participants were statistically significant; farmers aged up to 47 years exhibited a positive attitude toward hydroponics systems in contrast to those above 47 years. In addition, female farmers were more willing to introduce hydroponics farming than male farmers. These findings revealed that implementing the hydroponic system would be effective among the youth and women.

Keywords: Hydroponic systems, Post-Pandemic Economy, Probit Model, Willingness

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